

Rethinking the Funding Paradigm for Secondary School Education in a Depressed Economy in Anambra State

¹ Vinella OKONTA ²Grace Nwamaka OSAKWE

¹Department of Educational Management and Foundations, Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria.

Email: vokonta@delsu.edu.ng

² Department of Educational Management and Foundations, Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria.

Email: osakweamaka@gmail.com

Abstract

The toll of inflation on the economy with its attendant consequence on the purchasing power and further worsened by poor budgetary allocation to education sector by successive government in Anambra state requires that principals in the state should rethink their funding paradigm for secondary school education. It is for this reason that the researchers embarked on the study christened 'rethinking the funding paradigm of secondary school education in a depressed economy in Anambra State'. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 263 registered public secondary school principals in Anambra state. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw a sample size of 105 respondents. A 13-item questionnaire titled 'Rethinking of secondary schools' Funding Alternatives in a Depressed Economy (RPFAD E)' was the instrument for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts from Faculty of Education, Delta State University, Abraka. Cronbach alpha method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The overall coefficient of 0.84 was obtained. The researchers with the help of two research assistants collected the data for the study. Mean was used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that public secondary school Principals do not effectively utilize the non-statutory funding alternatives. Accordingly, it was recommended that principals should be sensitized on the need to be more creative and forward looking; and explore other funding alternatives other than the statutory allocations from the government.

Keywords: Funding; Paradigm; Secondary Education; Depressed Economy

Introduction

The delivery and sustainability of efficient and quality education that will reflect the global needs expressed in twenty first century world, revolves around the wheels of fund. Without sufficient funds, the infrastructural needs, training and retraining of human capital and equipping the teachers who in turn prepare the students that will help bring about socio economic changes for national growth and development would become a mirage. Nwafor, Uchendu and Akani (2015) posit that funding is considered all over the world as the life wire that propels the educational sector towards achieving its objective. They further argued that the level of success recorded by the educational sector has been closely linked to the availability of resources and that among the resources needed for the effective administration of the educational sector, funding has been identified as an indispensable instrument. This explains why UNESCO recommends 26% of the annual budget of any nation to be earmarked for education to help bolster the quality and quantity of educational provisions (Ugwu, Chime and Agu 2020).

In spite of UNESCO's recommendation, the albatross for Nigeria's education sector has continued to be poor funding (Ndujihe, 2019). Agbai, Okafor, and Egbedoyin (2021) in a comparative study of education funding in Nigeria reported that between 2009 and 2019, 12.05% and 12.46% of the annual national budget for years 2014 and 2015 respectively were the highest national education budgets allocated to the various levels of education in Nigeria in recent years. These figures fall short of what is expected for the nation's educational industry to be adequately catered for.

Secondary school education is critical to the education of a child. It is regarded as the bridge between primary and tertiary education (Ige, 2019). Among all the levels of education, secondary education is considered very crucial because it serves as a link between tertiary and primary. More so, a major factor that necessitates the provision of secondary education in Nigeria is that education at the primary level seems to be insufficient for a child to acquire permanent literacy, communicative and numeracy skills that are expected at the end of the training (Ugwu, Chime and Agu, 2020). Secondary schools in Nigeria are categorized as either public or private. Public secondary schools are post-primary institutions of learning established, controlled and financed by the government.

Public secondary schools receive funding from government in form of capital projects and recurrent expenditures. Abubakar, Shika and Habiba (2020) posit that government and other educational stakeholders in Nigeria seem to ignore funding of educational programmes and activities for the system to grow, function and operate effectively. They went further to submit that government as the leading stakeholder in the educational sector has the responsibility of making statutory provisions in terms of

funding school programmes in different ways which include but not limited to the following: development of school infrastructures: funding of teacher training and retraining programmes, provision of facilities and equipment such as laboratories, libraries, books, ICT facilities, employment of teaching and non-teaching staff and payment of their salaries, funding and monitoring of educational policy implementation, building and maintenance of school infrastructures, provision of teaching aids, building and maintaining educational inspectoral units, providing schools with good nutrition among others. In addition to these provisions expected from the government, schools can creatively think outside the box and develop strategies on how to take advantage of other opportunities that exist outside the statutory government provisions. Bluehaven (2019) advised that schools can take advantage of the following opportunities to increase their revenue base: Parents Teachers Association (P.T.A.) contributions, use of direct labour, payment for extra lesson, proceeds from school activities, fund raising, community involvement, alumni donations, non-governmental organization, school fees, international organizations, school activities, community effort, Education Tax Fund (ETF), rentals, grants, endowments/donations ,corporate efforts/activities amongst others.

From the foregoing, it behooves on secondary school principals to adopt and rethink their fund-raising practices especially at this period of insufficient budgetary allocation to education as a result of worsening economic depression. By so doing, Nwamaradi (2022) insists that principals will then help to explore and effectively assess and utilize both the statutory and the non statutory funding alternatives in a manner that funds will become sufficiently available to provide qualitative and decent learning environment and opportunities.

The argument as to whether male principals are better in terms of fund raising and fund management abilities than their female counterpart is raging and requires empirical resolution. Anukaenyi, Ene and Nwafor (2022) observed that irrespective of gender, principals need a variety of administrative competencies and skills such as good personnel management, involving staff in decision-making, communicating freely with them and ability to manage school finance properly. Nelson (2012) posits that there is a tendency among women to have a higher degree of fund risk aversion than men. They went further to submit that women would take a lower risk when managing an investment or sourcing for funds and that men and women are similar in their level of confidence as it relates to financial decisions. Whether the principal is a male or female, the need and challenge of taking right decisions that will bring about availability of funds to cope with the seemingly insatiable financial needs is the same and quite compelling.

Anambra state is one of the states notable for huge financial commitments to secondary education. However, the decrepit conditions of public secondary schools infrastructures and noticeable needs for

learning facilities across some secondary schools in both rural and urban centres in the state would seemingly suggest that principals are not effectively engaged in practices that will help them to leverage on the funding alternatives that will bring enough funds for school improvement especially at this period of dire economic depression. It is against this background that this study was conceived.

Statement of the problem

Provision of quality education that will meet the needs of the people in twenty first century world is capital intensive. Governments at all levels, Anambra state inclusive, have abundantly demonstrated their inability to fund education alone. Anambra state secondary school principals are faced with the challenge of engaging in funding practices that will help them to explore the statutory and the non-statutory funding alternatives of secondary education. However, the level of infrastructural decays, poor sanitary conditions, yearning needs for learning materials, other sundry needs and challenges plaguing public secondary schools in the state appear to have become the common features of most schools. If this trend is not reversed promptly, the future of secondary education in the state will come under serious threat. Hence, this study will analyze the principals' funding alternatives in a depressed economy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the principals' statutory funding practices for secondary school education in a depressed economy?
2. What are the principals' non-statutory funding alternatives practices for secondary school education in a depressed economy

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on their statutory funding practices for secondary school education in a depressed economy.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on their non-statutory funding alternative practices for secondary school education in a depressed economy.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested. All the 263 registered public secondary school principals in Anambra state made up the population for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw a sample size of 105 respondents. A 13-item questionnaire titled "Rethinking of secondary schools' Funding Alternatives in a Depressed Economy (RPFAD E)" was the instrument for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts from Faculty of Education, Delta State University,

Abraka. Cronbach alpha method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The overall coefficient of 0.84 was obtained. The researchers together with the help of two research assistants collected the data for the study. Mean was used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. 105 copies of questionnaire were distributed and 93 copies retrieved, indicating 88% return rate. Any item with mean score of 2.50 and above is taken as agreement and any item below 2.50 is considered as disagreement. In testing the null hypotheses, if the t-calculated is greater or equal to t-critical at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypotheses is considered significant, otherwise, the null hypotheses is considered not significant.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the principals’ statutory funding alternatives for secondary education in a depressed economy?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on Male and Female Principals’ statutory funding alternatives for secondary education in a depressed economy

S/N	ITEMS	MALE PRINCIPALS (N = 32)			FEMALE PRINCIPALS (N = 61)			TOTAL (N = 93)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Anambra state government provides fund for payment of salaries.	3.17	1.07	Agreed	2.82	1.11	Agreed	2.99	1.10	Agreed
2	The state funds non recurrent expenditures.	2.72	1.06	Agreed	2.60	.99	Agreed	2.66	1.01	Agreed
3	Government makes funds available to principals for maintenance of school facilities.	2.10	1.11	disagreed	1.90	1.07	disagreed	2.00	1.08	disagreed
4	Government provides funds for training and retraining of teachers.	2.67	1.14	Agreed	2.72	1.07	Agreed	2.70	1.10	Agreed
5	Instructional materials are provided by the government.	2.75	.86	Agreed	2.57	1.09	Agreed	2.67	.95	Agreed
6	Government provides equipment for scientific experiments	2.82	1.01	Agreed	2.77	1.01	Agreed	2.79	1.05	Agreed
Mean of means’		2.70	1.04	Agreed	2.56	1.05	Agreed	2.63	1.04	Agreed

Table1 revealed that all the items fall within the range of 2.50 and above indicating that male and female principals agreed that government provides funds for all the requirements listed in the items except for item 3 with mean scores of 2.10 and 2.00 for male and female principals respectively. This indicates that principals agree that government does not make funds available for maintenance of school facilities. The overall mean of means of 2.70 and 2.63 for male and female principals indicate that they agree unanimously that statutory funding options of secondary schools are sourced largely from government. This is because government allocate funds for salaries, facilities and instructional materials. This finding

confirms the study earlier conducted by Igbe, Nnabuike and Otegbulu (2016) whose study revealed that government contribute to a great extent towards improving the funding of secondary education in Anambra state. The agreement in the findings of the two studies could be as a result of proximity in time and similarity in government policies. The present study is equally in agreement with the study of Obi, Okpala and Ezemba (2021) whose study shows that government establishes and provides good welfare for teachers, provides adequate policies and have more qualified teachers. The agreement in the findings of the two studies may not be unconnected to similarity in location, research method and proximity in time lag for the two studies.

The standard deviation scores of 1.04 and 1.05 for male and female principals respectively indicate homogeneity in the responses of the principals. It further indicates that gender is not a factor that can significantly affect the outcome of this study. This is because government provides funds to schools irrespective of the principals' gender. Hence, no significant difference exists in the mean ratings of male and female principals on their statutory funding alternatives for secondary school education in a depressed economy such as Anambra state. The finding of this study is in agreement with the findings of Ugwu (2017) whose study showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on the extent of their engagement in academic performance monitoring activities for sustainable quality assurance in secondary schools in Anambra state. Agreement in the findings of the two studies may be attributed to same location, time proximity and same respondents.

Research Question 2: What are the principals' non-statutory funding alternatives for secondary education in a depressed economy?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on Male and Female Principals' non-statutory funding alternatives for secondary education in a depressed economy

S/N	ITEMS	MALE PRINCIPALS (N = 32)			FEMALE PRINCIPALS (N = 61)			TOTAL (N = 93)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Funds are sourced from PTA	2.60	1.07	Agreed	2.72	1.11	Agreed	2.68	1.10	Agreed
2	My school is funded through proceeds from the school farm	2.13	1.06	disagreed	2.20	.99	disagreed	2.18	1.01	disagreed
3	My school is funded through donations from private individuals	2.17	1.11	disagreed	2.23	1.07	disagreed	2.21	1.08	disagreed
4	My school is funded through endowment funds	2.27	1.14	disagreed	2.22	1.07	disagreed	2.24	1.10	disagreed
5	Alumni raise funds to support the school projects	1.86	.86	disagreed	2.06	.99	disagreed	1.99	.95	disagreed
6	Community is involved in school funding	2.38	1.01	disagreed	2.20	1.01	disagreed	2.26	1.05	disagreed
7	The school organizes fund raising activities	1.90	.99	disagreed	2.25	.99	disagreed	2.13	1.07	disagreed
Mean of means'		2.18	1.03	Disagreed	2.26	.88	Disagreed	2.24	1.05	Disagreed

Table 2 revealed that all the items fall within the range of 2.27 and below indicating that both male and female principals disagreed that non- statutory funding options provide funds for schools’ financial needs except for item 1 with mean scores of 2.60 and 2.68 for male and female principals respectively. This indicates that principals agree that except for parents’ teachers’ association, other non-statutory funding options such as funding through proceeds from the school farm, donations from private individuals among others, are not effectively harnessed. The overall mean of means of 2.18 and 2.26 for male and female principals indicate that they agreed unanimously that non-statutory funding options of secondary schools are not effectively harnessed. This is because these sources of funding are not common practices in the school system. They are used occasionally. This study is in agreement with the study of Ubi and Egwu (2022) whose study showed that there was low extent in utilization of farm proceeds and other non-statutory funding options by principals in secondary schools in Cross River state. The agreement in the findings of the two studies may be connected to time proximity. Whereas Ubi and Egwu conducted their study in 2022, the present study was conducted in 2024. Similarity in research design and respondents could also account for the agreement in the findings. The finding of this study is consistent with the finding of Onyeukwu (2022) whose study shows that alternative sources of financing secondary school education in Abakaliki Education Zone of Ebonyi State include; the use of Parents Teachers Association (PTA), proceeds from school activities, and fund-raising activities among others.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on their statutory funding practices for secondary school education in a depressed economy.

Table 3: t-test Comparison of male and female Principals’ Mean Ratings of Their statutory funding alternatives for secondary education in a depressed economy

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Male	32	2.70	1.04	91	0.37	0.00	Sig
Female	61	2.56	1.05				

Table 3 shows that the mean score for male secondary school principals ($M=2.70$, $SD=1.04$) was not significantly greater than that of female secondary school principals ($M=2.56$, $SD=1.05$); $t(91) 0.37$, $p=.000$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on their engagement in statutory funding practices was therefore accepted.

Hypothesis 2 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female principals on their non-statutory funding alternative practices for secondary school education in a depressed economy.

Table 4: t-test Comparison of male and female Principals’ Mean Ratings of Their non-statutory funding alternatives for secondary education in a depressed economy

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Male	32	2.18	1.03	91	7.63	0.00	Sig
Female	61	2.26	.88				

Table 4 indicates that the mean score for male secondary school principals ($M=2.18, SD=1.03$) was not significantly less than that of female school principals ($M=2.26, SD=.88$); $t(91) 7.63, p=.000$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on their engagement in non-statutory alternative funding practices was therefore accepted.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, there are statutory funding alternatives available to both male and female principals. The non-statutory funding alternatives available to principals for secondary school education in Anambra state are not effectively harnessed.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. Principals should make farming part of the school programme and utilize the proceeds there-from to augment the statutory allocations they receive.
2. Principals should from time to time organize activities like launchings to raise funds for the schools.
3. Communities should also be sensitized by the school on the need to invest and participate in funding school projects.
4. Principals should encourage alumni to be more regular in their financial commitment to the schools.

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